

Visualizing Multidrug Resistance: A Rapid Scoping Review Protocol

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Background

Multidrug resistance (MDR) is an important factor in the problem of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and AMR surveillance, but it is complex to describe MDR in a clinically relevant way because there are so many potential MDR phenotypes for each bacterial species. Most antibiograms present limited information on MDR, such as the percentage of isolates that are MDR, defined as resistance to three or more antimicrobial classes. However, this information is not always clinically relevant for veterinarians, and it is a crude indicator of MDR trends. A scoping review will be conducted to identify similar initiatives or projects, including methods, metrics, analysis, and visualization approaches used for MDR surveillance, as well as the boundaries and limitations of these approaches. The results of the scoping review will allow us to develop novel MDR analysis metrics and visualizations to incorporate MDR data into AMR dashboards.

Objective

To identify visualization approaches, including metrics and analysis methods used to generate visualizations, for MDR data among bacterial populations from any host population.

Review Question

Problem: Multidrug resistant bacteria in animals, humans, and the environment

Concept: Visualization approaches

Context: Last 15 years (2008 - 2023)

Search strategy development

The search strategy was developed by identifying several relevant papers and dashboards already known to the authors, then creating a list of keywords from those examples.

Dashboards and publications that were identified as examples are in Appendix A.

Evidence gathering

The following databases were searched for published manuscripts and abstracts:

- PubMed (Medline)
- CAB Abstracts
- Web of Science
- IEEE Xplore
- ACM Digital Library

For dissertations and theses:

- ProQuest Dissertations and Theses

For gray literature:

- Google search

Databases were identified based on their relevance to the topic and ability to perform complex searches. Details on the search strategies are found in Appendix A. Search strategies were refined with a goal of identifying fewer than 2000 results per database. When possible, results were limited to publications from 2008 to 2023. An application to scrape results from Google search was then developed in Python. Since the goal of this project is to perform a rapid review, backwards or forwards reference searches were not conducted.

Searches conducted:

Database	Search Used	Date Searched	Number of Results	File name
PubMed	Appendix A: PubMed #1 AND #2 AND #3 AND #4 NOT #5	10/31/23	1,240	Pubmed 10-31-23.csv (and txt)
Web of Science Core Collection	Appendix A: Web of Science #1 AND #2 AND #3 AND #4 NOT #5	10/31/23	1,123	Web of Science 10-31-23 1001-1123.xls (and RIS) Web of Science 10-31-23 1-1000.xls (and RIS)
ProQuest Dissertations and Theses	Appendix A: ProQuest #1 AND #2 AND #3 AND #4 NOT #5	10/31/23	42	ProQuestDocuments-2023-10-31.xls (and RIS)
CAB Abstracts (CABI Digital Library)	Appendix A: CAB Abstracts #1 AND #2 AND #3 AND #4 NOT #5	11/1/23 (end date 10/31/23 for inclusion)	591	cabi (#).csv (12 files) cabi (#).ris (6 files)
IEEE Xplore	Appendix A: IEEE XPLORE #1 AND #2 AND #3 AND #4 NOT #5	11/1/23	911	IEEE 10-31-23.xls (and 10 RIS files from 11/1/23)

ACM Digital Library Full Text Collection	Appendix A: ACM #1 AND #2 AND #3 AND #4 NOT #5	10/31/23	150	acm 10-31-23.txt (and enw and bib)
Google Grey Literature	Appendix A: Google each string searched individually	11/1/23	612	GoogleSearch_search_string_2023_10_31.xls (6 files) and RIS files (6 files, 11/1/23)

Study selection

Inclusion Criteria

- Text available in English
- Published between 2008 - 2023
- Describes or includes a visualization or display of multidrug resistance in a bacterial population

Those studies that did not meet any one of the above inclusion criteria were excluded from the review.

Title/Abstract Screening Questions

- I. Is the text available in English?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
- II. Is the text published in the past 15 years (2008 - 2023)?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
- III. Does the text examine antimicrobial resistance data among a bacterial population?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
 - C. Uncertain
- IV. Does the text contain or describe at least one visualization of multi-drug resistance, defined as the relationship between two or more drug resistances (phenotypic or genotypic)?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
 - C. Uncertain

If No to any question, exclude.

If Yes or Uncertain to all questions, move to full text review.

Full Text Screening Questions

- I. Is the text available in English?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
- II. Is the text published in the past 15 years (2008-2023)?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
- III. Does the text examine antimicrobial resistance data among a bacterial population?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
- IV. Does the text contain or describe at least one visualization of multi-drug resistance, defined as the relationship between two or more drug resistances (phenotypic or genotypic)?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No

If No to any question, exclude.

If Yes to all questions, include.

Review Process

All citations identified in the search process will be added to SWIFT Active Screener (Sciome)^{1,2}. SWIFT Active Screener uses an Active Learning model to rank the relevance of documents, iteratively updating the model when the review team includes or excludes documents.

All reviewers will initially review 100 randomly selected documents to assess reviewer agreement and refine the screening criteria for clarity and consistency. Conflicts will be discussed and screening questions, eligibility criteria, and protocols will be adjusted as needed.

These 100 documents will form the beginning of the training set for SWIFT Active Screener. The review team will continue including documents in the training set, with two reviewers screening each document title/abstract. The documents will be presented in order of predicted relevance. Any disagreement among reviewers will be resolved by discussion of the entire review team. Documents will be screened until 95% recall is achieved or half of documents are screened, whichever comes first.

Data extraction

Full text review and data extraction will occur at the same time. Data from all eligible studies will be charted using a standard form, which will be designed after initial screening. The data extraction form will be used by the review team to identify relevant information and detailed data from eligible studies. The full text review and data charting process will be tested on 5 studies.

Data synthesis

The data extracted from all eligible studies will be analyzed and summarized using figures and tables. The data synthesis plan will be updated when the data extraction form is created.

Dissemination

Results from this rapid scoping review will be presented in abstracts at national or international conferences, and a manuscript will be drafted for publication.

Acknowledgements

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Appendix A. Search Strategy

Examples used to develop search strategy:

Example AMR Dashboards:

- Global Antimicrobial Resistance and Use Surveillance System (World Health Organization)
- Global Database for Tracking Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) Country Self- Assessment Survey ([TrACSS](#)) (WHO, FAO, WOAHA)
- Antimicrobial Resistance in Europe (European Food Safety Authority)
- ResistanceMap (One Health Trust)
- Antimicrobial Resistance Dashboard (British Columbia Center for Disease Control)
- NARMS Now (US National Antimicrobial Resistance Monitoring System)
 - <https://www.fda.gov/animal-veterinary/national-antimicrobial-resistance-monitoring-system/2020-animal-pathogen-amr-data>.

Example Papers:

- Robert D. Stedtfeld, Maggie R. Williams, Umama Fakher, Timothy A. Johnson, Tiffany M. Stedtfeld, Fang Wang, Walid T. Khalife, Mary Hughes, Brett E. Etchebarne, James M. Tiedje, Syed A. Hashsham, **Antimicrobial resistance dashboard application for mapping environmental occurrence and resistant pathogens**, *FEMS Microbiology Ecology*, Volume 92, Issue 3, March 2016, fiw020, <https://doi.org/10.1093/femsec/fiw020>
- Ruzante JM, Harris B, Plummer P, Raineri RR, Loy JD, Jacob M, Sahin O and Kreuder AJ (2022) **Surveillance of antimicrobial resistance in veterinary medicine in the United States: Current efforts, challenges, and opportunities**. *Front. Vet. Sci.* 9:1068406. doi: 10.3389/fvets.2022.1068406
- Rumi, MV, Nuske, E, Mas, J, Argüello, A, Gutkind, G, Di Conza, J. **Antimicrobial resistance in bacterial isolates from companion animals in Buenos Aires, Argentina: 2011–2017 retrospective study**. *Zoonoses Public Health.* 2021; 68: 516–526. <https://doi.org/10.1111/zph.12842>

Example Websites:

- Veterinary Laboratory Investigation and Response Network (Vet-LIRN)
 - FDA x LDL collaboration

- National Animal Health Laboratory Network (NAHLN)
 - National Animal Health Monitoring System (NAHMS) → domestic poultry
- CDC EID Journal, Antimicrobial Resistance Spotlight: <https://wwwnc.cdc.gov/eid/spotlight/antimicrobial-resistance>
- CDC AR Threats Reports: <https://www.cdc.gov/drugresistance/biggest-threats.html>
- CDC Transatlantic Taskforce on Antimicrobial Resistance: <https://www.cdc.gov/drugresistance/tatfar/index.html>
 - TATFAR Data for Action Fact Sheet: TATFAR. *Data for Action: Using Available Data Sources to Track Antibiotic Use in your Country*. February 2019. www.cdc.gov/DrugResistance/TATFAR.
- GLASS-EAR Module: <https://www.who.int/initiatives/glass/glass-focused-surveillance>

Example Keywords

Multi-Drug Resistance (MDR):

- MDR Phenotypes
 - Resistance Phenotypes
 - MDR Phenotype Frequency
 - MDR Phenotype Associations
 - Clinically Relevant MDR Phenotypes
 - Clinically Relevant Pathogenic Phenotypes
- MDR Pathogens
 - High-Consequence MDR Pathogens
- MDR Trends
 - MDR and Resistance Co-Selection
 - MDR Inter-Class Associations
 - Concurrent Antimicrobial Use
 - Sequential Antimicrobial Use
- Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing
 - Bacterial AST
 - Antimicrobial Susceptibility Status and Pathogens

Visualization:

- Graphics
- Dashboard
- Map
- Trends and Displays
 - Over Time
 - Regional, Spatial Analysis, longitudinal study
 - Prevalence of, in (Region)
 - Surveillance, Surveillance of
 - Tracking
 - Dashboard

Database Search Strings:

Medline (PubMed)

#1	//Antimicrobial terms - All Fields "multidrug" OR "multi-drug" OR "co-resistan*" OR "MDR" OR "drug resistance, multiple" [MeSH]
AND #2	//Resistance terms - All Fields "resist*" OR "susceptib*" OR "sensit*" OR "efficacy"
AND #3	//Surveillance Terms - All Fields "surve*" OR "prevalen*" OR "track*" OR "monitor*" OR "report*" OR "detect*" OR "analy*" OR "trend*" OR "frequen*" OR "pattern*" OR "distribut*" OR "characteriz*"
AND #4	//Figure and Dashboard terms - All Fields "map" OR "maps" OR "mapp*" OR "spatial" OR "geospatial" OR "dashboard" OR "plot*" OR "visual*"
NOT #5	// - All Fields "cancer" OR "malaria" OR "parasit*" OR "viral" OR "virus" OR "tumor" OR "protein"

CAB Abstracts

#1	//antimicrobial terms - All fields multidrug OR multi-drug OR co-resistan* OR MDR
AND #2	//resistance terms - All fields resistan* OR susceptib* OR sensit* OR efficacy
AND #3	//Surveillance Terms - All fields surve* OR prevalen* OR track* OR monitor* OR report* OR detect* OR analy* OR trend* OR frequen* OR pattern* OR distribut* OR characteriz*
AND #4	//Figure and Dashboard terms - All fields map OR maps OR mapp* OR spatial OR geospatial OR dashboard OR plot* OR visual*
NOT #5	- All fields cancer OR malaria OR parasit* OR viral OR virus OR tumor OR protein

Web of Science

#1	//antimicrobial terms - All Fields "multidrug" OR "multi-drug" OR "MDR" OR "co-resistan*"
AND #2	//resistance terms - All Fields "resistan*" OR "co-resistan*" OR "susceptib*" OR "sensit*" OR "efficacy"

AND #3	//Surveillance Terms - All Fields "surve*" OR "prevalen*" OR "track*" OR "monitor*" OR "report*" OR "detect*" OR "analy*" OR "trend*" OR "frequen*" OR "pattern*" OR "distribut*" OR "characteriz*"
AND #4	//Figure and Dashboard terms - All Fields "map" OR "maps" OR "mapp*" OR "spatial" OR "geospatial" OR "dashboard" OR "plot*" OR "visual*"
NOT #5	- All Fields "cancer" OR "malaria" OR "parasit*" OR "viral" OR "virus" OR "tumor" OR "protein"

IEEE Xplore

Limited to 9 wildcards per search, but automatically applies stemming (plurals and verb forms) (e.g., "ignite" finds "igniting" and "ignited").

#1	//antimicrobial terms - Full text and metadata multidrug OR multi-drug OR co-resistant OR co-resistance OR MDR
AND #2	//resistance terms - Full text and metadata resistan* OR susceptib* OR sensit* OR efficacy
AND #3	//Surveillance Terms - Full text and metadata survey OR prevalen* OR track OR monitor OR report OR detect OR analy* OR trend OR frequen* OR pattern OR distribut* OR characterize
AND #4	//Figure and Dashboard terms - Full text and metadata map OR spatial OR geospatial OR dashboard OR plot OR visual*
NOT #5	- Full text and metadata cancer OR malaria OR parasit* OR viral OR virus

ACM Digital Library

#1	//antimicrobial terms - Anywhere "multidrug" OR "multi-drug" OR co-resistan* OR "MDR"
AND #2	//resistance terms - Anywhere resistan* OR susceptib* OR sensit* OR "efficacy"
AND #3	//Surveillance Terms - Anywhere surve* OR prevalen* OR track* OR monitor* OR report* OR detect* OR analy* OR trend* OR frequen* OR pattern* OR distribut* OR characteriz*

AND #4	//Figure and Dashboard terms - Anywhere "map" OR "maps" OR mapp* OR "spatial" OR "geospatial" OR "dashboard" OR plot* OR visual*
NOT #5	- Anywhere "cancer" OR "malaria" OR parasit* OR "viral" OR "virus"

ProQuest Dissertations and Theses

#1	//antimicrobial terms - Anywhere except full text multidrug OR multi-drug OR co-resistan* OR MDR
AND #2	//resistance terms - Anywhere except full text resistan* OR susceptib* OR sensit* OR efficacy
AND #3	//Surveillance Terms - Anywhere except full text surve* OR prevalen* OR track* OR monitor* OR report* OR detect* OR analy* OR trend* OR frequen* OR pattern* OR distribut* OR characteriz*
AND #4	//Figure or Dashboard terms - Anywhere except full text map OR maps OR mapp* OR spatial OR geospatial OR dashboard OR plot* OR visual*
NOT #5	- Anywhere except full text cancer OR malaria OR parasit* OR viral OR virus OR tumor OR protein

Google Search (each string searched individually)

#1	multidrug resistance dashboard
#2	antimicrobial resistance dashboard
#3	antimicrobial resistance surveillance
#4	multidrug resistance surveillance
#5	multidrug resistance graph
#6	multidrug resistance meta-analysis

References

1. Howard BE, Phillips J, Tandon A, et al. SWIFT-Active Screener: Accelerated document screening through active learning and integrated recall estimation. *Environ Int.* 2020;138:105623. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2020.105623
2. Elmore R, Schmidt L, Lam J, et al. Risk and Protective Factors in the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Rapid Evidence Map. *Front Public Health.* 2020;8. doi:10.3389/fpubh.2020.582205